

This is the Preprint Version for 5GSmartFact

Official Open Access Link:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2542660524002105>

C-SLA-MLO: Enhancing SLA Compliance in Industrial Wi-Fi through Cooperative Multilink Operation

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Multilink Operation
IEEE 802.11be
SLAs
Wi-Fi 7

ABSTRACT

In the dynamic landscape of Industry 4.0, robust wireless connectivity emerges as a critical enabler for Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) applications. With the advent of Wi-Fi 7's multilink operation (MLO), the demand for schedulers capable of meeting diverse Service Level Agreement (SLA) requirements within industrial environments becomes paramount. Addressing this need, this paper introduces Cooperative SLA-MLO (C-SLA-MLO), a novel distributed multilink scheduler that balances data across MLO channels to fulfill the SLA of STAs operating within the same BSS. We provide a simulation-based evaluation where we compare C-SLA-MLO with other benchmark approaches, in terms of SLA compliance when varying the SLA characteristics, the level of QoS, or background traffic, showcasing an average reduction of 90% in SLA deviation in the industrial use case. This study contributes practical insights for enhancing wireless connectivity in IIoT, offering potential benefits for industrial network optimization by exploiting the MLO feature brought by the new IEEE 802.11be.

1. Introduction

Industrial communication technologies are undergoing a significant transformation to realize the vision of Industry 4.0, with the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) playing a pivotal role in providing scalable, sustainable, and intelligent solutions. IIoT is defined as the interconnected network of intelligent industrial components that are strategically deployed to enhance production efficiency while lowering operational costs. This is achieved through real-time monitoring, effective management, and control of industrial processes, assets, and operational timelines[1]. Current IIoT communications can be divided into those used for critical operations (e.g. safety, control, and monitoring applications), which are often implemented using custom industrial Ethernet technologies like Profinet and Ethercat [2], and those used for non-critical operations (e.g. alerting, supervisory control, and data-logging tasks), typically implemented using Wi-Fi or other wireless IoT technologies [3]. The future vision of IIoT communications consists of transforming communications for critical operations in two steps. First, replacing custom industrial Ethernet technologies with standardized Ethernet Time Sensitive Networking (TSN) technology, thus reducing costs. Second, extending Ethernet TSN technology with wireless connectivity to gain agility in re-defining manufacturing layouts [4]. Both 5G NR and Wi-Fi 8 are candidate enabling technologies to achieve the vision of wireless TSN.

Extending Ethernet TSN concepts to the wireless domain poses challenges in terms of network architecture and performance guarantees. In terms of network architecture, integration of IEEE 802.11 and Ethernet TSN is straightforward, as both technologies are based on IEEE 802.1 [5]. In the case of 5G, 3GPP has defined an integration model based on TSN-Translator functions, whereby a set of User Equipment (UEs) and the core network behave as a single Ethernet TSN switch [6]. The primary challenge is to deliver comparable performance assurances through wireless technologies as those offered by Ethernet TSN. For example, the TSN framework includes Time-Aware Scheduling (TAS), as defined in IEEE 802.1Qbv [7], which allows bounded end-to-end latencies by defining a set of scheduled gates at each switch port. Reliability is also enhanced using redundant paths, using the Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability (FRER) mechanism defined in IEEE 802-1CB [8]. Studies have investigated the implementation of these ideas within the context of 5G applied to industry 4.0 [9]. In the case of Wi-Fi though, given its contention-based access and the use of unlicensed spectrum, the progress towards a deterministic latency and reliability has been more limited. However, the IEEE 802.11be, certified as Wi-Fi 7, has set the goal of extremely high throughput, and the recently formed IEEE 802.11bn group, the basis of the future Wi-Fi 8, has set enhanced ultra-high reliability as its main goal. Motivated by IEEE 802.11be and bn, the focus of this paper is to advance the state-of-the-art for reliable, and (quasi) deterministic Wi-Fi for IIoT applications.

The IEEE 802.11be amendment introduces multilink operation (MLO) as a key feature to enhance performance. Notably, an advanced feature like Multi AP coordination is postponed until the subsequent IEEE 802.11bn amend-

ORCID(s):

ment. As discussed throughout this paper, MLO plays a pivotal role in enhancing timeliness for Wi-Fi transmissions by simultaneously leveraging multiple links, thereby reducing latency. Furthermore, MLO contributes to improved reliability by enabling the transmission of duplicated packets across various links, and the aggregation of multiple links results in a noteworthy boost in overall throughput. These characteristics collectively position the MLO feature as a compelling solution for addressing the stringent timeliness requirements in industrial applications.

IIoT applications exhibit diverse Service Level Agreement (SLA) requirements for time-critical applications. These range from safety applications demanding a deterministic delay bound around 10 ms (e.g. emergency actions or leak detection), to control and monitoring applications with more flexible requirements spanning from 10 ms to 100 ms [3]. This diversity underscores the need for wireless standards that can cater to the varied SLA demands of industrial scenarios. To the best of our knowledge, there is currently no proposed IEEE 802.11be's MLO scheduler specifically tailored to meet diverse SLAs in an industrial context. Existing schedulers often employ a greedy approach, prioritizing minimal latency for a single time-critical application. However, this strategy may not be optimal for industrial scenarios with a range of SLA requirements. In [10], we proposed SLA-MLO, the first SLA-driven MLO scheduler that dynamically selects the link based on the SLA of a particular flow. This approach distinguishes itself by not adhering to a greedy strategy and instead aims to align with the diverse nature of IIoT application requirements, ranging from stringent and time-sensitive to highly flexible time constraints. The essential Key Performance Indicator (KPI), optimized by SLA-MLO, is the measurement of SLA deviation, representing the extent to which a flow deviates from its prescribed limits, specifically the delay bound value.

Building upon this foundation, the present study presents a cooperative SLA-MLO, that allows STA in the same BSS to exchange information about the SLA compliance status of their flows, to optimize the resources allocated to flows suffering from SLA deviations. C-SLA-MLO is able to further decrease SLA violations up to 90% in industrial use cases. The main contributions of the present work are as follows:

- We provide a comprehensive taxonomy of multilink schedulers proposed to date, analyzing their feasibility in specific scenarios.
- We propose an extension of SLA-MLO[10] called Cooperative SLA-MLO (C-SLA-MLO), that further improves the SLA deviation of time-critical flows by enabling coordination among STAs, thereby allocating more resources to flows that are not meeting their SLAs.
- We implement C-SLA-MLO in NS-3 simulator, and benchmark its performance in terms of SLA deviation against SLA-MLO and Least Congestion Control (LCC) [11].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we first discuss the basics and architecture of MLO, and present different multilink schedulers proposed in the past. In section 2.2, we discuss the design of C-SLA-MLO. In section 4, we provide a comprehensive performance evaluation through different simulation setups that justify our design choices. Lastly, section 5 summarizes our conclusions and findings.

2. Background and related work

In this section, we discuss the motivation, basic concepts, and architectural details behind MLO. In a second subsection, we provide a related literature review.

2.1. Multilink operation

The crowded ISM bands pose limitations on wide-channel transmissions, which impacts the maximum potential of technologies like Wi-Fi 7 supporting up to 320MHz bandwidth. Nevertheless, through strategic spectrum allocation across various bands, we can capitalize on opportunities for broader channels, leading to enhanced throughput and a significant reduction in latency. MLO plays a crucial role in enabling these advancements by facilitating data transmission and reception across multiple radio interfaces, effectively optimizing spectrum utilization across the 2.4 GHz, 5 GHz, and the newly allocated 6 GHz bands.

The architecture of Multilink Devices (MLD), is distinct from legacy devices, featuring two main types: AP-MLD and non-AP MLD (i.e. client STAs) that contain Upper and Lower MAC layers. The Upper MAC is uniform across links, managing tasks like sequence numbering, and common functions. The Lower MAC, replicated for each available link, handles tasks like channel access and packet transmission. Each link runs an independent physical

layer. The central concern in MLD is optimizing multilink usage within a device, particularly through scheduling, as discussed in the next section.

Depending on the devices capabilities, MLD can be categorized in different ways, as discussed in [12].

- Multilink Single Radio (MLSR): where a device is capable of transmitting and receiving data over one link at a time.
- Enhanced Multilink with Single Radio (EMLSR): where a device is capable of receiving data over multiple links using different MIMO RF chains, while transmitting over one link at a time by tracking channel availability across all links.
- Multilink Multi-Radio (MLMR): where a device contains multiple radios and is able to operate on multiple links concurrently. MLMR can be further categorized as:
 - Non-Simultaneous Transmit and Receive (NSTR): where a device is capable of either receiving or transmitting on multiple links at the same time, requiring alignment or deferral of physical layer protocol data units to prevent overlap and ensure smooth operation.
 - Simultaneous Transmit and Receive (STR): where a device is capable of concurrent transmission and reception of data asynchronously, but requires careful management to prevent inter-device interference to ensure smooth operation.
- Enhanced Multilink Multiple Radio (EMLMR): where a device features the capability to reconfigure MIMO chains on each link for improved performance and flexibility.

The first available MLO-capable Wi-Fi 7 devices are expected to support single-radio MLO, leveraging existing Wi-Fi 6 hardware. However, as Wi-Fi 7 advances, new STAs will harness the advantages of incorporating multiple radios. Besides, in the IIoT domain, devices requiring reliable connectivity, such as robots or PLCs, are often power connected and are not resource-constrained. Hence, we can assume that MLO will be introduced through MLMR-STR devices, which support simultaneous transmission and reception through multiple radios.

Figure 1: Taxonomy of MLO schedulers proposed in the literature

The MLO scheduler is a crucial component in multilink devices, playing a key role in their performance. It usually works at the (Upper) MAC layer and controls the transmission of packets among different radio interfaces. The design of the MLO scheduler influences how effective, adaptable, and reliable MLDs are, especially in challenging IIoT environments.

Table 1

Overview of proposed schedulers for IEEE 802.11be's Multi-Link Operation and their applicability

Sn.	Method	Scenario	TSN Application	KPIs	Type	SLA-Awareness
1	Load balancing (LB) [13]	High network load	Cyclic industrial traffic of motion control with 100 and 1400 byte packet size and inter-packet gap 1 to 10 ms	Latency	Static	No
2	Packet duplication(PD) [13]	Low network load			Static	No
3	Packet splitting(PS) [13]	Low network load			Static	No
4	Hybrid (LB+PS+PD) based on global information [14]	Medium and dynamic network load			Dynamic	No
5	Least congestion control [11]	Dynamic traffic in controlled scenario	General traffic flows 2-8 Mbps	Channel occupancy and throughput	Dynamic	No
6	Congestion aware load balancing [11]	Uncontrolled and denser scenarios			Dynamic	No
7	Separate data and signaling channels [15]	Large and medium sized packet with high priority	Voice traffic	Delay quantile and efficiency	Static	No
8	Allocating a dedicated channel [15]	Long transmission			Static	No
9	Splitting dedicated channel into sub-channel [15]	Long transmission with intensive and smaller size packet			Static	No
10	SLA aware scheduling called SLA-MLO [10]	Industrial use case	Industrial scenario having stringent SLAs of delay bound of 1 ms and flexible SLAs of upto 10 ms	SLA deviation	Dynamic	Yes

2.2. MLO schedulers

Recently, various methods have emerged for implementing multilink scheduling within IEEE 802.11be networks, aimed at enhancing the latency, reliability, and throughput of time-sensitive data. Figure 1 depicts a taxonomy of multilink schedulers proposed in the literature. Each of these approaches is well-suited to a specific scenario. These schedulers have been categorized into two categories, static and dynamic. In a static approach, the scheduling mechanism remains fixed throughout the network's lifetime, regardless of varying traffic conditions. Conversely, in a dynamic approach, the scheduling undergoes dynamic changes over time. The static scheduler includes load balancing (LB), which distributes load among available links, to reduce latency [13], packet duplication (PD), which duplicates the same packets onto multiple links for improving reliability [13], packet splitting (PS), involves breaking down packets into smaller chunks and transmitting them in parallel across multiple links, thereby enhancing data rate [13].

Additionally, channel segregation [15], is another technique, which can be categorized according to the channel allocation. This includes allocating distinct signaling channels for individual data channels, designating a dedicated channel specifically for time-critical data, or dividing this dedicated channel further into smaller sub-channels for more granular data management. A dedicated channel serves well for long transmissions with stringent latency needs, while splitting it further proves beneficial for smaller, high-volume traffic. For scenarios with a large number of flows having varying traffic profiles, a dedicated resource scheme does not scale well.

On the other hand, dynamic approaches adapt link-selection policies using information available at the STA, including both global (network-wide) information, and STA or flow-specific. In [14], authors propose a scheduler for improving the reliability and latency of industrial cyclic traffic by introducing a hybrid approach that selects links by applying PB, PS, or LB according to global information. In [11], the authors compare different policies that are updated based on a link congestion metric. These policies include least congestion control (LCC) that selects links with lesser congestion, as well as both static and dynamic load balancing approaches that take into account the congestion level at each link, namely congestion-aware load balancing (CALB). The authors performed simulations considering controlled and uncontrolled traffic scenarios. They concluded that LCC performs well in a controlled environment, while CALB performs better in uncontrolled and dense scenarios. However, note that these policies were fixed for the entire life of a flow. In [16], the same authors extended their prior work and suggested that the above policies can be further improved in terms of latency if they are adapted dynamically.

Despite the vast potential of this groundbreaking technology in diverse settings, there is a notable gap in the

literature regarding the practical application of IEEE 802.11be's MLO in industrial and factory-like environments. Specifically, there is a lack of proposals that comprehensively study MLO in scenarios involving multiple flows with varying requirements or SLAs, which are common in IIoT environments. For instance, a collaborative robot may require a tight delay bound of 5 ms [17], while a human-machine interface (H2M) may have a more relaxed delay bound of 50-200 ms [18]. Therefore, a different approach is needed to cater to the specific requirements imposed by different traffic flows. It is worth noting here that MLO schedulers proposed in the literature do not explicitly define an SLA, i.e. they try to improve performance in a best-effort way. However, in [19], the authors emphasize various applications, traffic profiles, and connectivity requirements critical from an IIoT perspective. These include isochronous flows, involving regular data transmission with fixed bandwidth and timing requirements, and cyclic traffic, characterized by a repeating pattern of events but with variable intervals. Such traffic patterns are fundamental for modeling IIoT environments, such as machine-to-machine and human-to-machine interactions using XR (Extended Reality) [20], for instance.

In [10] we proposed the first SLA-based scheduler called SLA-MLO, which selects links, based on the SLA of particular flows on a per-packet basis, using locally available delay statistics. It was concluded that, in industrial use cases, i.e. presence of multiple flows having different SLAs, the SLA deviation of SLA-MLO improved by almost 50% when compared with LCC. Table 1 summarizes the suitability of proposed schedulers, KPIs for which they have been tested, and TSN application configuration.

Figure 2: Network model considered for this work. Background STA1 to STA3 represent legacy devices with single-link capabilities, while the production line (SLA-STA1) and collaborative robots (SLA-STA2) are equipped with multilink capabilities, featuring SLA flows. The lower diagram illustrates the packet handling process at SLA-STAs.

3. Design of C-SLA-MLO

3.1. Network Model

In Figure 2, we depict the system model considered in this study. The configuration includes two types of IEEE 802.11be STAs and a multilink-enabled Access Point (AP).

- Background STAs: generate non-SLA flows (i.e. non time critical traffic) on legacy Wi-Fi devices with single-link connections. The purpose of these STAs is to create background traffic. In Figure 2, STA1 to STA3 are

background STAs.

- SLA-based STAs: MLD-STAs responsible for transmitting a diverse set F of flows, each denoted as $f \in \mathbf{F}$, and associated with its specific SLA (such as delay bound and allowed percentage of SLA breach). In Figure 2, production line and collaborative robots are using MLD-STAs for transmitting data flows to the MLD-AP

The lower segment of Figure 2 provides insight into the internal architecture of an MLD device. The operational sequence initiates with the reception of packets at the MAC layer of the MLD-STA coming from the upper layers. Following, packets are classified based on their associated flow $f \in \mathbf{F}$. Under the influence of the specific SLA linked to that flow, the scheduler steers the packet towards a designated link $i \in \mathbf{L}$ with a probability denoted as $P_{f,i}$. The primary objective of the SLA-based scheduler is to dynamically and adaptively determine the values of $P_{f,i}$ for each flow f and link i . It is important to note that all MLD STAs depicted in Figure 2 are assumed to be STR-capable. Consequently, Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA/CA) rules are applied independently in all enabled links. In this work, we have considered uplink traffic.

3.2. SLA definition

In the realm of IIoT applications, the synchronization of data and control signal flows with the manufacturing process's cycle time stands as a critical consideration. The efficiency and performance of the process are significantly impacted by latency, with cycle times ranging widely — from less than 1 ms for field bus communications to several hundred milliseconds for controllers communicating with edge devices [18]. We defined SLAs as follows:

Delay Threshold (D_TH_f): maximum permissible delay from when a packet belonging to flow f is received from the ingress queue until it receives a successful acknowledgment.

In environments characterized by the use of unlicensed spectrum and contention-based access (e.g. Wi-Fi networks), defining SLAs encounters significant obstacles. As a result, an exclusive reliance on stringent delay bounds for SLA definition proves impractical in this context. Hence, we added another concept in SLA, defined as follows:

Error Threshold ($Error_TH_f$): percentage of packets of flow f that are allowed to exceed D_TH_f .

The objective of the schedulers is then to ensure that the percentage of packets in flow f exceeding D_TH_f remains below $Error_TH_f$ within measurement window T_{SLA} .

3.3. Working of SLA-MLO and Cooperative SLA-MLO

3.3.1. SLA-MLO

In [10], we proposed SLA-MLO, designed for MLD-STAs, operates on a per-flow, per-packet basis to optimize communication in alignment with predefined SLAs. When a packet is generated at an STA, the algorithm calculates link probabilities ($P_{f,i}$). Two critical parameters, the delay bound and SLA breach, guide decision-making. If a flow f adheres to the delay bound (D_TH_f) and stays below the allowed SLA breach level ($Error_TH_f$), all links receive the same probability. Conversely, if the SLA breach is above the threshold value, links showing a delay within the delay bounds are prioritized. However, if none of the links adheres to the delay bound and the SLA breach exceeds the threshold, the probability $P_{f,i}$ becomes a function of link delay, ensuring adaptability to diverse network conditions and minimizing the impact of congestion.

Algorithm 1 outlines the operation of the MLD-STA scheduler for a specific flow f . Input parameters include the SLA definition for flow f denoted by $(D_TH_f, Error_TH_f)$. Internal variables are maintained for each flow, including STA delay (STA_Delay_f), which denotes the total duration of transmitting a packet and receiving an acknowledgment, the link delay ($Delay_{f,i}$), experienced by packets of flow f in link i , Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) of link delays ($AvgDelay_Link_{f,i}$), and SLA breach metric (SLA_Breach_f).

The algorithm outputs probabilities $P_{f,i}$ for transmitting the next packet of flow f over link i . The algorithm begins with the *Main Scheduler Loop()* when a packet arrives from the upper layer. Before queuing, probabilities for each link are calculated using Procedure 3, involving SLA_Breach_f computation from Procedure 1. In Procedure 1, delay metrics are updated upon receiving acknowledgment, and SLA breach is determined based on D_TH_f (line 5 to line 10). Procedure 3 calculates probabilities based on two states:

- State 1: If SLA breach is below $Error_TH_f$, all links receive equal probabilities, as shown in *AlgorithmSelection()* line 18.
- State 2: If SLA breach is above $Error_TH_f$ (line 27 to 31).

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for the SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO scheduler. Decision at an MLD-STA for flow f .

```

1: procedure 1: UPON RECEIVING ACK
2:   Get Ack of the last successful packet
3:   Measure  $STA\_Delay_f$  &  $Delay_{f,i}$ 
4:    $AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i} \leftarrow AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i} \cdot \alpha$ 
5:      $+ Delay_{f,i} \cdot (1 - \alpha)$ 
6:   if  $STA\_Delay_f \leq D\_TH_f$  then
7:      $SLA\_Followed \leftarrow SLA\_Followed + 1$ 
8:   else
9:      $SLA\_NotFollowed \leftarrow SLA\_NotFollowed + 1$ 
10:  end if
11:   $SLA\_Breach_f \leftarrow \frac{SLA\_NotFollowed}{SLA\_Followed + SLA\_NotFollowed}$ 
12: end procedure
13: procedure 2: ALGORITHM SELECTION
14:  if  $Beacon\_SLA\_Breach = true$  then
15:     $k = \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in L} \{AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i}\}$ 
16:     $P_{f,k} = 1$ 
17:  else
18:     $P_{f,i} \leftarrow \frac{1}{|L|}$ 
19:  end if
20: end procedure
21:
22: procedure 3: CALCULATE PROBABILITY
23:   $L_{below} \leftarrow \{i \in L | Delay_{f,i} < D\_TH_f\}$ 
24:   $L_{above} \leftarrow \{i \in L | Delay_{f,i} \geq D\_TH_f\}$ 
25:  if  $SLA\_Breach_f \leq Error\_TH_f$  then
26:     $AlgorithmSelection()$ 
27:  else if  $|L_{below}| \neq 0$  then
28:     $P_{f,(i|i \in L_{above})} \leftarrow 0$ 
29:     $P_{f,(i|i \in L_{below})} \leftarrow \frac{1}{|L_{below}|}$ 
30:  else
31:     $P_{f,(i|i \in L)} \leftarrow \frac{1/AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i}}{\sum_{i \in L} 1/AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i}}$ 
32:  end if
33: end procedure
34:
35: procedure MAIN SCHEDULER LOOP
36:  while true do
37:    Wait for packet assigned to flow  $f$ 
38:     $P_{f,i} \leftarrow CalculateProbability()$ 
39:     $Rn \leftarrow uniform(0, 1)$ 
40:     $prob \leftarrow 0$ 
41:    for  $i \in L$  do
42:       $prob \leftarrow prob + P_{f,i}$ 
43:      if  $Rn < prob$  then
44:        forward the packet to link  $i$ 
45:      end if
46:    end for
47:  end while
48: end procedure

```

– Case 1: assigns equal probabilities to links still having delay below D_TH_f as shown in *Procedure3()*, line 27.

- Case 2: assigns probabilities inversely proportional to link's average delay, as shown in *Procedure3()*, line 30.

After probability calculation, the algorithm generates a random number R_n . If the number is less than the cumulative probability, the packet is forwarded to the link's outbound queue, prioritizing higher probability links.

In summary, SLA-MLO dynamically adapts to network conditions, prioritizing SLA compliance and favoring links with lower delays during breaches. It offers a flexible approach to real-time traffic distribution based on network state.

3.3.2. Cooperative SLA-MLO

We have enhanced SLA-MLO by introducing modifications in the algorithm, resulting in C-SLA-MLO. When at least one MLD STA is the transmitter of a flow failing to meet its SLA, it notifies the other MLD-capable STAs. Said notification could be accomplished in different ways, by leveraging different procedures outlined in the IEEE standard [21], such as the Transmit Stream/Category Measurement report or Multicast Diagnostics report. To elaborate, when an MLD STA detects that one of its flows is not meeting the SLA, it informs the AP using a triggered report, by setting a certain flag. When SLA violation vanishes, it again notifies the AP by means of another triggered report. Upon receiving these notifications, the MLD-capable AP would trigger a flag (*Beacon_SLA_Breach*) in the beacon, indicating that at least one STA is failing to meet its SLAs. All MLD STAs monitor the beacon to be notified about the status of other STAs. If the *Beacon_SLA_Breach* is set in this beacon field, then all MLD STAs activate C-SLA-MLO. The key modification can be found in procedure 2 of Algorithm 1. In SLA-MLO, when SLA_Breach_f is below the allowed threshold, all links receive the same probability (line 18). However, in C-SLA-MLO, as discussed earlier, *Beacon_SLA_Breach* is set to be *true* by AP, and for all flows that are adhering their SLAs, the link experiencing the highest congestion is selected with probability 1 (line 14 to 16). This adjustment aims to improve SLA-MLO's performance by directing more flexible traffic flows to links supporting more congestion, thereby creating additional space for flows with stringent requirements.

The fundamental distinction between SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO arises when a network encounters situations where flows with stringent requirements fail to meet their SLAs, while flexible flows adhere to their specified SLAs (i.e. delay bounds and SLA breach are below the threshold). In such instances, SLA-MLO uniformly allocates flows having flexible SLA across all links. In contrast, C-SLA-MLO takes a more strategic approach by directing this traffic specifically to congested links. This strategic adjustment aims to optimize the overall performance by enabling less congested links to handle more traffic from flows with stringent SLAs. On the other hand, C-SLA-MLO also requires an established notification mechanism to trigger the solidarity of flexible flows, whereas in SLA-MLO, STAs operate autonomously without requiring any signaling exchange.

4. Performance evaluation

To evaluate the performance of different schedulers, we used NS-3 (V3.36) [22], a packet-level simulator, which we adapted to support MLO. MLO capability was added to the MAC-level implementation of NS-3, which is already split into upper MAC and lower MAC. The upper MAC encompasses common functionalities such as sequence number assignment, active probing, and association-related mechanisms. The Lower MAC level, consists of three modules:

1. **Channel Access Manager (CAM)**: this module manages channel access, including Distributed Coordination Function (DCF) and Enhanced Distributed Channel Access (EDCA).
2. **Frame Exchange Manager (FEM)**: responsible for handling IEEE 802.11 amendment-specific frame exchange sequences.
3. **TXOP (Transmission Opportunity)**: along with its subclass QOS-TXOP, it manages queueing functionalities.

For the implementation of the MLO feature in NS-3, separate channel and frame exchange managers per link are necessary. A unified *TXOP* with distinct queues for each MLO link was constructed. When the Upper MAC decides to send a packet to a link, based on the scheduler decision, the *TXOP* assigns the corresponding packet to the corresponding queue. After placing the packet in the designated queue, the corresponding *FEM* and *CAM* are invoked. Following the execution of lower MAC functionalities, the *FEM* assigns the frame to a particular Wi-Fi Phy (Wi-Fi physical layer entity).

4.1. General simulation setup

Unless specified otherwise, the simulated scenarios presented in this section share the following characteristics. Each scenario contains N number of STAs and 1 AP. To make the simulation more realistic, nodes were randomly deployed within a 15-meter radius of the AP in every setup, and by default, MLD nodes included two radios in the 6GHz band. In IIoT environments, other bands are used for non-critical operations, which is why we focus on the greenfield 6 GHz band to provide guaranteed performance. There are two types of STAs, as discussed in the network model depicted in Figure 2, i.e. legacy devices transmitting non-SLA flows and MLD-STAs transmitting flows with specific SLAs.

To represent the heterogeneity of SLAs across flows in IIoT environments, two types of MLD STAs were employed, each with distinct SLA requirements.

- The *Stringent* type has a strict delay bound, below 5 ms, used for example in isochronous flows for control loops [19], and a 5% of SLA breach threshold (STA1).
- The *Flexible* type has a more relaxed delay bound of up to 50 ms, used for example in monitoring applications for industry [3],[19], and a 10% of SLA breach threshold.

Each scenario includes one stringent STA alongside multiple backgrounds and flexible STAs. All simulations adhered to the system model outlined in Figure 2. Each simulation has been run for at least 10 different seeds.

To benchmark the performance of C-SLA-MLO and SLA-MLO, we use a dynamic approach for congestion control, known as Least Congestion Control (LCC), proposed in [11]. This method keeps track of the congestion levels to select the least congested link.

Key Performance Indicator (KPI): based on the SLA definition provided in Section 3.2, we evaluate the level of SLA compliance for a flow in terms of SLA-deviation. The calculation of SLA-deviation is outlined as follows:

For each SLA flow f , we measure the percentage of packets with a delay surpassing D_{TH_f} at regular intervals of t_{sample} , resulting in a time-varying signal $Error_f(t)$. To assess SLA compliance, we compute the moving average of $Error_f(t)$ within a window of duration T_{SLA} using a convolution operation:

$$Avg_error_f(t) = Error_f(t) * \left(\frac{1}{T_{SLA}} \right) Sq(t) \quad (1)$$

Here, $Sq(t)$ represents a square signal with a duration of T_{SLA} seconds. Subsequently, the SLA deviation for flow f is computed as:

$$SLA_dev_f(t) = \max(Avg_error_f(t) - Error_TH_f, 0) \quad (2)$$

It's important to emphasize that the metric $SLA_dev_f(t)$ only increases when flow f surpasses its SLA's error threshold. If the flow remains below the error threshold, the metric remains unchanged, as there are no discernible benefits from the application perspective.

4.2. Evaluation scenarios

We structure our performance evaluation in six different scenarios that answer the following research questions.

- Scenario 1: in the first scenario, we show the dynamics of proposed schedulers.
- Scenario 2: the second scenario studies how increasing the number of flexible flows influences the performance of stringent flows under different schedulers.
- Scenario 3: in the third scenario, we study the effect of SLA heterogeneity, on the performance of the schedulers. The goal is to study how sensitive SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO gains are, to the difference between the strict and the relaxed SLAs.
- Scenario 4: the fourth scenario involves the evaluation of different QoS settings. The goal is to study the effect of MLO scheduling combined with EDCA prioritization.
- Scenario 5: in the fifth scenario, we introduce a third link on MLD devices. The motivation behind this experiment is to check how MLO schedulers behave when we increase the number of links.
- Scenario 6: In the final scenario, we reproduce realistic industrial scenario featuring 6 industrial flows and random background traffic. To substantiate our assertion regarding the effectiveness of a multilink scheduler tailored for IIoT environment, it is imperative to conduct a performance evaluation within a setting closely resembling a practical IIoT environment.

Table 2 shows the general parameters of the simulation setup.

Table 2

Overview of general simulation parameters

Feature	Simulation Parameter
Frequency Band	6GHz (channel number 15 & 47)
Channel Width	160MHz
Standard	IEEE 802.11ax
Aggregation Mode	OFF
MCS	Minstrel
Background STAs throughput	1500B / ms
Simulation time	30s (per simulation)
Packet Queue size	500p (per link)
Traffic Type	Uplink
Propagation model	Log Distance Propagation Loss Model

4.2.1. Scenario 1: Understanding the dynamics of SLA-MLO & C-SLA-MLO

This experiment is intended to show the behavior of both SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO under different traffic conditions.

Simulation setup: 1 stringent flow with 0.750 ms of delay bound and an error threshold of 5% and 5 flexible flows with 50 ms of delay bound and 10% of error threshold. SLA flows are transmitting 64B packets every 2.5 ms, i.e. 204.8 Kbps, and background STAs are transmitting at the rate of one 1500B packet per ms, i.e. 12 Mbps.

Discussion: in Figure 3, we plot the output of algorithm 1 i.e. probabilities of links for stringent flows (Figure 3a for C-SLA-MLO and Figure 3b for SLA-MLO) and for flexible flows (Figure 3d). Figure 3c shows the SLA breach of the stringent flows. The simulation is divided into 3 phases.

- During the first 10s of simulation, there is no background traffic on either link, resulting in near-zero SLA breach for both stringent and flexible flows in both schedulers. Consequently, probabilities of selecting link 1 or link 2 in the stringent flow are 50% for both links (Algorithm 1, line 18).
- Between 10s and 20s, congestion occurs only on link 1, causing a 5% SLA breach for the stringent flow (close to its D_{TH_f}), while link 2 maintains low delay values. Consequently, both for C-SLA-MLO and SLA-MLO, link 2 tends to have higher probabilities for the stringent flow, with $Error_{TH_f}$ providing flexibility for occasional testing of link 1 (Algorithm 1, lines 27 to 29). Flexible flows(c.f. Figure 3d) adhere to their SLAs, resulting in 50% probabilities for both links in SLA-MLO, but in C-SLA-MLO, STAs with flexible flows are occasionally notified that the stringent flow is failing to meet its SLA and therefore, the congested link 1 receives a higher probability (Algorithm 1, 26).
- Between 20s to 30s, in the final phase, link 1 experiences lesser congestion than link 2 (3:6 Background traffic), resulting in the stringent flow selecting link 1 with a higher preference both for SLA-MLO and for C-SLA-MLO (Algorithm 1, line 31). C-SLA-MLO and SLA-MLO differ in how the flexible flows react. While both schedulers maintain flexible flows' adherence to their SLAs, SLA-MLO assigns equal probabilities to both links. However, being informed that the stringent flow fails to meet its SLA, the flexible STAs running C-SLA-MLO, assign higher probabilities to the congested link 2. Consequently, stringent flows in C-SLA-MLO encounter less congestion in link 1, resulting in a lower SLA breach compared to SLA-MLO, as depicted in Figure 3c.

Please note that the pattern of probabilities for the links of all flexible flows under both schedulers is consistent with the pattern demonstrated for one of the flows shown in Figure 3d.

In summary, the distinction between the two schedulers becomes evident when stringent flows breach their SLAs while flexible flows remain SLA-compliant. This scenario is observed between 20s to 30s. In SLA-MLO, equal probabilities are assigned to both links for flexible flows, whereas C-SLA-MLO, is able to balance resources between stringent and flexible flows in a better way, by directing flexible flows to the congested link, allowing more room for stringent flows. Consequently, stringent flows experience less congestion in C-SLA-MLO, resulting in lower SLA breaches compared to SLA-MLO.

4.2.2. Scenario 2: Impact of growing number of MLD devices

The objective of this experiment is to demonstrate the behavior of different schedulers when legacy devices are substituted with MLD-enabled devices, which support SLA flows. Notice that when the load in the network is generated by legacy STAs, MLO schedulers have less opportunities to balance load. This changes as the number of MLD devices in the network grows.

Simulation setup: these simulations include four distinct types of STAs, as detailed in Table 3. First, five background STAs transmit on link 1, while higher congestion is generated in link 2 by connecting 10 background STAs. Throughout each iteration, we systematically replace legacy or single-link devices with MLD-STAs featuring flexible SLAs, transitioning from DNoSLA STAs to DRelaxed STAs. Notice that when replacing DNoSLA flows by DRelaxed flows the overall load in the network remains the same, but the MLO schedulers have more opportunities to balance flows across links 1 and 2.

Figure 3: Demonstration of dynamics of proposed schedulers. Figure a) and b) illustrate the probabilities of link 1 and link 2 for Stringent flows under both C-SLA-MLO and SLA-MLO, respectively. Figure c) outlines SLA breaches for both scenarios, while Figure d) presents the probabilities of flexible flows on both links.

Discussion: Figure 4a illustrates the SLA deviation experienced by the stringent SLA flow, while the DNoSLA STA are replaced by DRelaxed STA in the x-axis. We can see the more legacy devices (DNoSLA) are replaced by MLD devices (with relaxed SLA), the better the delay performance of the stringent SLA flow, when C-SLA-MLO is used. This improvement is attributed to the introduction of relaxed flows, which offer the added flexibility of accepting more congested paths, thereby creating space for stringent flows in the less congested link. Neither SLA-MLO nor LCC benefit from a higher number of MLD devices in this scenario. Figure 4b, shows the percentage of packets sent through the most congested link for each scheduler. As the number of MLD STAs increases, the presence of a strict flow not meeting its SLA forces C-SLA-MLO to send more (relaxed) packets through congested links, thus leaving more resources to stringent flows in the fastest links. C-SLA-MLO, clearly outperforms the other approaches, especially in the presence of 6 or more MLD STAs. In the case of SLA-MLO, the average percentage of relaxed

Figure 4: Performance evaluation with increasing number of MLD devices. Figure a) shows the SLA deviation of the stringent flow, and Figure b) shows the percentage of packets through the congested link.

Table 3

Scenario 2 simulation setup

Type	Definition	SLAs	Data rate	Num. of STAs
DStringent	SLA flows with strict SLA requirements	1 ms and 5%	700B / 10ms	1
DRelaxed	SLA flows with relaxed SLA requirements	5 ms and 40%	700B / 10ms	0-10
DNoSLA	Similar to DRelaxed but installed on non-MLD STAs, having no SLA requirements	No	700B / 10ms	10-0
Background	Flows with no SLA requirement	No	1500B / ms	5 link 1, 10 link 2

Table 4

Scenario 3 simulation setup

(a) Flow settings in Heterogenous setup

Flow #	Error Threshold	Delay bound
1	5%	1 ms
2-11	10%	6.25 to 100 ms

(b) General settings

Feature	Simulation Parameter
SLA flows Data Rate	64B / 5 ms
Background STAs	5:10 (link1 : Link2)
Stringent Vs Flexible Flows	1:10 (Stringent: Flexible)

flow is 50% on both links, since both links allow those flows to meet their SLA. On the other hand, all LCC STAs follow a selfish behavior, always trying to gain access through the fastest link, regardless of the SLA requirements. It is worth noting here that SLA deviation of all relaxed flow is zero, as they are still below an error threshold value. When compared to SLA-MLO and LCC, C-SLA-MLO manages to reduce SLA deviation up to 50%.

4.2.3. Scenario 3: Impact of SLA heterogeneity

We have seen in the previous experiment that C-SLA-MLO performs well, especially in the presence of relaxed flows that can afford balancing more load through more congested links. Now we want to see how sensitive this gain is to the difference in SLA between the strict and the relaxed flows.

Simulation Setup: Table 4 summarizes the simulation setup for this experiment. In this setup, we fix the number of relaxed flows to ten while modifying their SLA flexibility by changing their delay bound from 6.25 ms to 100 ms. Like in the previous experiment, link 2 is more congested than link 1.

Figure 5: Introducing heterogeneity by changing the delay bound of flexible flows. Figure a) shows the SLA deviation of stringent flow and Figure b) shows the percentage of packets through congested link.

Table 5

Scenario 4 simulation setup

(a) Flow settings in QoS setup

Flow #	Error Threshold	Delay Bound
1	5%	2 ms
Relaxed flows (2 to onwards)	10%	50 ms

(b) General settings

Feature	Simulation Parameter
SLA flows Data Rate	64B / 5 ms
Background STAs ratio at start	4:9 (link1 : Link2)
Stringent Vs Relaxed Flows at start	1:9 (Stringent : Flexible)
AC_BK	CW(15, 1023)
AC_VI	CW(15, 63)
AC_VO	CW(7,15)

Discussion: in Figure 5a, a clear pattern emerges as we progressively increase the delay bound for flexible flows, both SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO show a substantial decrease in SLA deviation, as measured for the stringent flow. Initially, the improvement is modest, mainly due to flexible flows breaching their own SLAs, thus willing to use the fastest links. However, as the delay bound expands, relaxed flows can tolerate more latency, creating leeway for stringent flows. Notably, C-SLA-MLO outperforms SLA-MLO by allocating more flexible traffic to congested links as the delay bound increases.

The effectiveness of SLA-MLO reaches a plateau beyond a 12.5 ms delay bound, as relaxed flows already contribute 50% of the traffic to congested links. Consequently, further extending the delay bound does not result in significant traffic allocation to congested links and, thus, does not yield further enhancements. In contrast, C-SLA-MLO can better exploit the growing delay bound of the flexible flows by allocating more flexible flows to the more congested link. This trend is depicted in Figure 5b, where the percentage of packets of flexible flows transmitted through the congested link (link 2), consistently increases with the delay bound.

Regarding LCC, its performance remains constant across all scenarios, as it doesn't adhere to SLA criteria. Overall, 35% of improvement can be seen in case of C-SLA-MLO in comparison with LCC and 20% in case of SLA-MLO.

4.2.4. Scenario 4: Assessing the impact of EDCA access categories

In our earlier experiments, we assumed identical EDCA settings for SLA flows and background flows. However, in real-world scenarios, SLA flows might be assigned a higher EDCA priority compared to background flows. This experiment seeks to investigate whether the performance improvements observed with C-SLA-MLO in the previous experiments persists when we

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6: Results with different QoS settings. One cluster consists of 1 flexible SLA flow and 2 background STAs on link1 and link2. Figure a) shows SLA flows with background (AC_BKG) settings, Figure b) shows SLA flows with video (AC_VI) settings and Figure c) shows SLA flows with voice (AC_VO) settings.

introduce different EDCA configurations across SLA and background flows using IEEE 802.11's own QoS management.

Simulation Setup: Table 5 summarizes simulation parameters for this experiment. Here, we increase background and SLA STAs in the form of clusters.

The simulation starts with four and nine background STAs on link 1 and link 2, respectively. The initial cluster, denoted as "cluster zero", includes one strict flow and nine relaxed flows. Subsequent clusters are formed by iteratively expanding the number of background STAs and introducing an additional relaxed flow. For example, Cluster 1 is formed by incorporating two background STAs and introducing one more relaxed flow (making it 10). QoS settings have been applied according to Table 5. Note that background traffic is always considered as AC_BK (i.e. the lowest priority in EDCA), while SLA flows are configured with different access categories in different experiments.

Table 6

Scenario 5 simulation setup

(a) Flow settings in 3 Links setup

Flow #	Error Threshold	Delay Bound
1	5%	2 ms
Relaxed flows (2 onwards)	10%	50 ms

(b) General settings

Feature	Simulation Parameter
SLA flows Data rate	64B / 5 ms
Background STAs ratio at start	10:10:5 (Link1:Link2:Link3)
Stringent Vs Relaxed Flows at start	1:10 (Stringent : Flexible)
Frequency Band	6GHz (channel number 15, 47 & 79)
Access Category for SLA Flows	AC_VI - CW(15,63)
Access Category for Background flows	Default (AC_BK)

Discussion: in Figure 6, three different QoS settings are depicted alongside the corresponding behaviors of the proposed SLA-based schedulers. Figure 6a portrays a baseline scenario where all flows are sent through AC_BK. As the number of clusters increases, the performance of all schedulers degrade as expected, since the network is becoming more congested. We observe that both SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO converge to a similar SLA deviation, outperforming LCC. Following the first cluster, deviations in compliance with SLA for flexible flows are observed. By the sixth cluster, these deviations escalate to exceed 10%. Consequently, the discernible difference in performance between SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO diminishes.

Figure 6b presents simulation results when SLA traffic is assigned to AC_VI and background traffic to AC_BK. As expected, the SLA deviation of the stringent flow decreases as compared to the scenario where all flows use AC_BK, because the AC_VI setting helps protect the stringent flow from the interference caused by background STAs. However, the stringent flow is still subject to interference from relaxed SLA flows that also use AC_VI. Interestingly, C-SLA-MLO demonstrates a superior performance when compared to both SLA-MLO and LCC. This can be attributed to the fact that relaxed flows in C-SLA-MLO facilitate directing a higher volume of traffic to congested links, creating more space for the stringent flows. While there is an improvement in SLA-MLO as well, it is less pronounced than in C-SLA-MLO since relaxed flows in SLA-MLO cannot direct more than 50% of traffic to congested links. SLA deviation for flexible flows in both SLA-aware schedulers is exceptionally low, approximately ranging between 1 to 2% (not shown in Figure 6 due to lack of space).

Figure 6c depicts the SLA deviation of the stringent flow when SLA flows are sent through AC_VO and background STAs use AC_BK. As expected, the SLA deviation for the stringent flow has been minimized to approximately 18% in the worst case (LCC). The gains of C-SLA-MLO over SLA-MLO and LCC are even more pronounced in this scenario. The reason for the observed gain is the same as in the AC_VI scenario. C-SLA-MLO is able to direct flexible flows towards the more congested link, allocating more resources to the stringent flows that are experiencing violations of their SLA. SLA deviation for flexible flows was zero in this setup.

Note that, for clarity, Figure 6 omits 3, 4, and 5 clusters in the X-axis since SLA deviations between them exhibit a consistent pattern.

In summary, SLA-MLO is constrained by its 50% traffic redirection limit, while C-SLA-MLO consistently outperforms due to its preference for congested links. Both schedulers perform similarly when flexible flows deviate from their SLAs. However, with a higher EDCA priority, C-SLA-MLO excels further. That is, SLA-aware scheduling in combination with EDCA prioritization for time-sensitive flows provides an even improved delay performance, especially in the case of C-SLA-MLO.

4.2.5. Scenario 5: Impact of number of links

In the previous experiments, we have considered only 2 links in each MLD device since we consider this to be the more common MLD implementation in the short term. In this section, we want to study how an additional radio link impacts the gains of C-SLA-MLO over the other schedulers.

Simulation setup: in Table 6, we summarize the simulation setup for this experiment. Link 1 and Link 2 are always more congested than link 3. We increase the number of clusters, starting with a 'zero cluster', where background STAs are present in a ratio of (10:10:5) across the three links. The increase in flows begins with a base configuration of (1:10) for stringent and flexible flows. Here, the term 'cluster' denotes the addition of one flexible SLA flow, along with the inclusion of three background STAs (one per link).

Discussion: Figure 7 depicts how the SLA deviation experienced by the stringent flow degrades as the number of clusters increases. However, both SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO demonstrate improvement in SLA deviation compared to LCC. This enhancement is visually represented in the Figure 8, where Figure 8a depicts the percentage of packets traversing link2 (congested)

Figure 7: SLA deviation of stringent flow for 3 link scenario. One cluster consists of 1 relaxed SLA flow and 3 background STAs on each link.

Figure 8: Flow percentage for the scenario with 3 links. One cluster consists of 1 relaxed SLA flow and 3 background STAs on each link. Figure a) shows the percentage of packets through the congested link and Figure b) shows the percentage of packets through a less-congested link.

and Figure 8b depicts the percentage of packets traversing link 3 (less congested). In Figure 8b, we can see how C-SLA-MLO exhibits a notably low average percentage of packets for flexible flows passing through less congested links (less than 10%), contrasting with SLA-MLO's consistent 33% and LCC's range of 45% to 60%. Moreover, a higher proportion of packets are directed through less congested links for strict flows in both SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO. Thus, even in a scenario with 3 radios per STA, C-SLA-MLO is able to allocate more often the less congested link to the stringent flows, in a more effective way than SLA-MLO or LCC. Overall, C-SLA-MLO showcases significant improvement compared to LCC, reducing deviation between 23% to 75%, with an average improvement of 35%. It's important to highlight that the SLA violation for flexible flows is zero and approximately 1% in the last case for C-SLA-MLO.

4.2.6. Scenario 6: Realistic industrial scenario

In the previous scenarios, we have considered artificial traffic patterns that have allowed us to better understand the factors governing the performance of the different MLO schedulers under study. However, in an industrial or factory-like scenario, multiple machines with different traffic patterns and QoS requirements need to interact seamlessly to ensure smooth and efficient operations. The objective of this experiment is to mimic a realistic industrial scenario by simulating real traffic models, data rates, and interference. This experiment is specifically tailored to assess the effectiveness of the proposed scheduler in an industrial context.

Figure 9: Industrial simulation setup, where Figure a) shows SLA-deviation of the motion control (stringent) flow and Figure b) shows the percentage of different flows on the most congested link.

Simulation Setup: in Table 7, we summarize most relevant parameters. We have chosen six industrial flows, where flow 1 represents motion control traffic and all others represent closed-loop control traffic (through mobile-connected I/O gateways), as proposed in [23]. It is noted here that flow 1 presents the most stringent SLA. In real industrial scenarios, background traffic can be periodic or aperiodic. Hence, we randomly assigned background traffic on and off time, i.e. each background STA will start and stop a background flow randomly, but at a fixed packet inter-arrival time. To test SLA deviation, we increased the number of background STAs while keeping Link 1 slightly less congested than Link 2 (40 Mbps and 46 Mbps, respectively). On average, we ensured that background flows last for at least 18 seconds out of the 30 seconds of simulation time.

Discussion: The SLA deviation for the motion control (stringent) flow in an industrial scenario is depicted in Figure 9. Notably, SLA-MLO and C-SLA-MLO exhibit remarkable performance compared to LCC in scenarios with dynamic background traffic in the industrial setting. Initially, the improvement is substantial, with C-SLA-MLO showing an average improvement of 73% compared to LCC and 48% compared to SLA-MLO. Additionally, SLA-MLO demonstrates a 60% improvement compared to LCC.

The increase in the number of background STA leads to an increase in SLA deviation for all SLA flows. As a consequence, relaxed flows (closed loop control) start failing to meet their SLAs thus moving packets to the faster link, leaving less room for stringent flow transmissions. In such instances, the improvement of C-SLA-MLO diminishes to 36% compared to LCC and 17% compared to SLA-MLO. For SLA-MLO, the improvement decreases to 22% compared to LCC.

The improvement in SLA deviation can be understood by looking at the flow percentage graph in Figure 9b. Initially, for C-SLA-MLO, the average percentage of relaxed flows through the congested link is high and decreases with an increase in background STAs. The number of stringent flows passing through the congested link is initially low but gradually increases over time, when the relaxed flows move away from the congested link. A similar trend is observed for SLA-MLO, where the percentage of flexible flows is around 50% on average on the congested link initially, but this percentage decreases after reaching a point of 12-16 background STAs. It is worth noting that here SLA deviation for flexible flows is 5% to 10% for C-SLA-MLO and up to 2.5% to 7% for SLA-MLO.

In summary, these results demonstrate the ability of C-SLA-MLO to better protect time-sensitive flows in realistic industrial scenarios. However, all schedulers suffer when the amount of background load in the channel exceeds the channel capacity. Admission control, limiting the number of background flows, would be required to limit SLA deviation in all situations.

5. Conclusion

In industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) scenarios, ensuring SLA compliance is paramount for maintaining operational efficiency and reliability, especially considering the diverse set of flows with varying SLA requirements prevalent in industrial environments. In this study, we introduced C-SLA-MLO, a cooperative multilink scheduling algorithm aimed at enhancing SLA adherence in industrial Wi-Fi networks leveraging the new MLO feature introduced in IEEE 802.11be. Through rigorous evaluation, we demonstrated significant performance improvements, with C-SLA-MLO achieving up to a 90% enhancement in SLA compliance compared to other approaches in industrial use cases.

Table 7

Scenario 6 simulation setup

(a) FLOW settings for industrial scenario

Flow #	Error Threshold	Delay Bound
1	5%	1 ms
2 to 6	10%	10 ms

(b) General Settings

Feature	Simulation Parameters
Frequency Band	6GHz & 5GHz
Channel Width	160MHz & 20MHz
Rate Control Algorithm	Minstrel
Flow1	Motion Control (64 B / 1ms) [23]
Flow 2 to 6	Close loop Control (64 B / 10ms)[23]
Background flow	Videos traffic (1500 B packet with data rate of 40 and 46.5Mbps in total on link1 and link2) [23]
Background STAs in Start	5:9 (Link1:Link2)
Stringent Vs Relaxed Flows	1:6 (Stringent : Flexible)

Our assessment encompassed six scenarios, each tailored to address specific research questions and assess the effectiveness of C-SLA-MLO in diverse network conditions. In Scenario 1, we showcased the dynamic adaptability of the proposed scheduler, highlighting its ability to prioritize flows based on SLA requirements. Scenario 2 explored the effect of augmenting the number of flexible flows on stringent flow performance, resulting in an improvement of up to 50% in SLA deviation. Meanwhile, Scenario 3 delved into SLA heterogeneity and its impact on scheduler gains, with enhancements of up to 35% in SLA deviation observed. Furthermore, Scenario 4 scrutinized the evaluation of diverse Quality of Service (QoS) settings, showing the combined effect of MLO scheduling with EDCA prioritization to optimize performance. Expanding our analysis, Scenario 5 introduced a third link on MLD devices to examine scheduler behavior in the context of increased link diversity, leading to a 30% improvement in SLA deviation. Finally, in Scenario 6, we simulated a realistic industrial environment featuring multiple industrial flows and random background traffic, reaffirming the effectiveness of C-SLA-MLO in practical IIoT settings. In this case up to 90% of improvement in SLA deviation was observed.

As for future work, we envision extending C-SLA-MLO to multi-AP scenarios to address larger-scale industrial networks and further enhance its adaptability to evolving network dynamics. Additionally, exploring optimization techniques for resource allocation and traffic management could offer additional insights into improving SLA compliance in complex industrial environments.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Discloure instrutions

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT 3.5 to enhance the readability of certain paragraphs within this paper. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

References

- [1] W. Z. Khan, M. H. Rehman, H. M. Zangoti, M. K. Afzal, N. Armi, and K. Salah. Industrial Internet of Things: Recent advances enabling technologies and open challenges. *Comput. Electr. Eng.*, 81, Jan. 2020.
- [2] X. Wu and L. Xie. End-to-end delay evaluation of industrial automation systems based on ethercat. In *2017 IEEE 42nd Conference on Local Computer Networks (LCN)*. IEEE, 2017.
- [3] E. Artetxe, O. Barambones, I. Calvo, P. Fernández-Bustamante, I. Martin, and J. Uralde. Wireless technologies for Industry 4.0 applications. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 16(3):1349, 2023.
- [4] M. Noor-A-Rahim, J. John, F. Firyaguna, H.H.R. Sherazi, S. Kushch, A. Vijayan, E. O'Connell, D. Pesch, B. O'Flynn, W. O'Brien, et al. Wireless communications for smart manufacturing and industrial IoT: Existing technologies, 5G and beyond. *Sensors*, 23:73, 2023.
- [5] A. Adame, M. Carrascosa-Zamacois, and B. Bellalta. Time-sensitive networking in IEEE 802.11be: On the way to low-latency Wi-Fi 7. *Sensors*, 21:4954, 2021.
- [6] L. Wisniewski L. Martenvormfelde, A. Neumann and L. Schreckenber. Co-configuration of 5G and TSN enabling end-to-end quality of service in industrial communications. <https://opendata.uni-halle.de/handle/1981185920/41505>, 2021.

- [7] Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Inc. Official website of the 802.1 time-sensitive networking task group, 2016. Accessed: 01.01.2024.
- [8] IEEE standard for local and metropolitan area networks—frame replication and elimination for reliability. *IEEE Std 802.1CB-2017*, pages 1–102, 2017.
- [9] A. Larrañaga, M. C. Lucas-Estañ, I. Martínez, I. Val, and J. Gozalvez. Analysis of 5G-TSN integration to support Industry 4.0. In *2020 25th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, volume 1, pages 1111–1114, 2020.
- [10] S. Kumar, E. García-Villegas, and D. Camps-Mur. Sla-mlo: Congestion-aware SLA-Based scheduling of multiple links in IEEE 802.11be. In *2024 IEEE 21st Consumer Communications Networking Conference (CCNC)*, pages 875–880, 2024.
- [11] A. López-Raventos and B. Bellalta. IEEE 802.11be multi-link operation: When the best could be to use only a single interface. In *2021 19th Mediterranean Communication and Computer Networking Conference (MedComNet)*, pages 1–7, Ibiza, Spain, 2021. IEEE.
- [12] IEEE P802.11 Working Group. IEEE P802.11be™/D5.0, November 2023 (amendment to IEEE P802.11-REVme™/D3.0). Draft Standard IEEE P802.11be™/D5.0. IEEE Computer Society LAN/MAN Standards Committee, Three Park Avenue, New York, New York 10016-5997, USA, November 2023. Draft Standard for Information technology—Telecommunications and information exchange between systems Local and metropolitan area networks—Specific requirements Part 11: Wireless LAN Medium Access Control (MAC) and Physical Layer (PHY) Specifications Amendment 8: Enhancements for extremely high throughput (EHT).
- [13] M.-T. Suer, C. Thein, H. Tchouankem, and L. Wolf. Multi-connectivity as an enabler for reliable low latency communications—an overview. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 22(1):156–169, 2019.
- [14] S. M. Theres, C. Thein, H. Tchouankem, and L. Wolf. Adaptive multi-connectivity scheduling for reliable low-latency communication in 802.11be. In *2022 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, pages 102–107. IEEE, 2022.
- [15] D. V. Bankov, A. I. Lyakhov, E. M. Khorov, and et al. On the use of multilink access methods to support real-time applications in Wi-Fi networks. *J. Commun. Technol. Electron.*, 66:1476–1484, 2021.
- [16] A. Lopez Raventos and B. Bellalta. Dynamic traffic allocation in IEEE 802.11be multi-link wlans. *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 11(7):1404–1408, 2022.
- [17] S. Sudhakaran, V. Mageshkumar, A. Baxi, and D. Cavalcanti. Enabling QoS for collaborative robotics applications with wireless TSN. In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, pages 1–6, 2021.
- [18] M. K. Atiq, R. Muzaffar, O. Seijo, I. Val, and H.-P. Bernhard. When IEEE 802.11 and 5G meet Time-Sensitive networking. *IEEE Open Journal of the Industrial Electronics Society*, 3:14–36, 2021.
- [19] D. Cavalcanti, C. Cordeiro, M. Smith, and A. Regev. Wi-Fi TSN: Enabling deterministic wireless connectivity over 802.11. *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, 6:22–29, December 2022.
- [20] M. Alsakati. Wi-Fi 7: Multi-Link Operation in XR Industrial Scenarios. Master’s thesis, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2022.
- [21] IEEE Computer Society. *IEEE Standard for Information Technology—Telecommunications and Information Exchange between Systems Local and Metropolitan Area Networks—Specific Requirements Part 11: Wireless LAN Medium Access Control (MAC) and Physical Layer (PHY) Specifications*. LAN/MAN Standards Committee, 2020. IEEE Std 802.11TM -2020 (Revision of IEEE Std 802.11-2016).
- [22] NS-3 Development Team. NS-3 Wi-Fi module design. NS-3 Documentation.
- [23] P.M. Rost and T. Kolding. Performance of integrated 3GPP 5G and IEEE TSN Networks. *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, 6(2):51–56, 2022.